

EFFICIENCY OF LONGITUDINAL GASTRIC RESECTION IN PATIENTS WITH OBESITY

Ravshanova Mokhibonu, Ibragimov Khasan

Samarkand State Medical University

Introduction

Longitudinal gastric resection (LRG) is a relatively new bariatric operation, first described as a restrictive stage of the operation - biliopancreatic shunting with the exclusion of the duodenum [1,2]. Since 2000, as the laparoscopic BPS technique has been mastered, LGR has increasingly begun to be performed as a deliberately first stage of an operation in patients suffering from superficial problems with a high operational risk. It was found that many patients after PRH reduced weight so much that the need for the second stage of the operation disappeared [3,4].

For the period 2004-2009 In the world, a little more than 15,000 LGR were performed, which amounted to only 5.3% of the total number of bariatric surgeries at that time, but in the future, the frequency of use of LGR gradually continued to increase.

Despite the fact that in recent years the LGR has been constantly discussed at all World and regional congresses and even at special thematic events, many issues related to both the indications for this operation and the technical nuances of its implementation are still not considered from a single positions.

The contingent of patients who underwent prostate cancer is also rather heterogeneous: from overweight to patients with a body mass index (BMI) of less than 40 and even less than 35 kg / m² [5]. The ambiguous results obtained in the analysis of rather heterogeneous groups of patients do not give a complete picture of the possibilities of this operation as an independent method of surgical treatment. Another controversial issue is the use of LGR in children and adolescents, as well as in patients with DM type 2 with slight overweight. And, perhaps, the least studied topic is the long-term outcomes of prostate cancer, since there are no significant cohorts of patients that could be traced within the specified time frame.

Purpose of the study

The aim of this study is to evaluate the effectiveness of LGR in patients with various degrees of obesity with a single method of performing the operation.

Materials and methods

From 2016 to 2019, 54 patients underwent laparoscopic prostatic surgery as a primary bariatric operation at 1 clinic of the SamSMI. The age of the operated patients ranged from 21 to 72 years (average age 42.6 ± 9.7 years), the male / female ratio was 1: 4.2, the average body weight of patients was 92.2 ± 16.2 , the average BMI was 37.2 ± 7.5 kg / m².

Table 1. Diseases associated with obesity in patients undergoing laparoscopic prostate cancer (n = 54)

Pathology name	n	%
Arterial hypertension	34	63.0%
Type 2 diabetes mellitus	17	31.5%
Pain in the joints of the extremities	31	57.4%
Lumbodynia	29	53.7%
Reflux esophagitis	42	77.8%
Ovarian dysfunction	19	35.2%
Bronchial asthma	5	9.3%
Cholelithiasis	fourteen	25.9%

Statistical data processing was carried out using the R studio 3.6.2 package. Statistically significant differences were determined by pairwise comparison of groups using Student's t-test. The results are presented as a sample mean and its error ($M \pm m$). The critical value of the significance level was taken equal to 0.05.

Results

In the early postoperative period, surgical complications were observed in 8 patients (14.8%) and included: gastric suture incompetence - 4 (7.4%), intra-abdominal bleeding - 2 (3.7%).

Table 2. Characteristics of the observed patients

BMI	Number of patients	Average BMI, kg	Average BMI, kg / m ²
Less than 35	18	72.8 ± 10.3	22.8 ± 1.1
35-40	9	86.5 ± 14.3	27.7 ± 1.4
40-45	13	97.5 ± 12.8	32.3 ± 1.5
45-50	9	115.5 ± 16.7	37.0 ± 1.2
Over 50	5	101.4 ± 13.7	45.4 ± 1.4
Total	54	93.6 ± 17.5	30.1 ± 4.7

The maximum average body weight loss (Table 3) was observed 12 months after PRV (33.2 ± 19.3), later the result worsened slightly (14.5 ± 12.5).

As the BMI increased, the maximum% EWL decreased, on the other hand, the tendency to regain lost weight after reaching the maximum became more distinct. Thus, the loss of excess body weight 6 months after prostate cancer in patients with a BMI from 40 to 45 kg / m² was $33 \pm 3.6\%$, and in patients with a BMI > 45 kg / m² - only $25.6 \pm 8.4\%$.

Table 3. Average loss of excess body weight after prostate cancer at different periods of follow-up (n = 54)

Observation period	Loss of excess body weight,%
3 months	47.4 ± 15.5
6 months	62.8 ± 18.2
9 months	72.1 ± 23.6
12 months	75.3 ± 22.5

22 patients (40.7%) had an excellent result (EWL > 75%), 15 (27.7%) had a good result (EWL 50-75%), 8 (14.8%) had an immediate (EWL 25 -50%). Only in 2 (3.7%) patients the result of the operation was unsatisfactory.

Thirty-seven patients (9 men and 28 women) were monitored for the likelihood of developing anemia after PRV. The initial parameters of hemoglobin in

patients averaged 1431.5 ± 12.42 g / l with fluctuations from 116 g / l to 152 g / l. The average hemoglobin level in women was 111.3 ± 15.9 g / l, in men - 132.4 ± 13.7 g / l. All patients after longitudinal gastric resection showed a significant decrease in hemoglobin parameters. On average, the hemoglobin content decreased 6 months after surgery by 21.37% from the initial level. In 5 (2 men and 3 women) out of 54 patients observed by us, the dynamics of hemoglobin indices (below 100 g/l) allowed us to diagnose iron deficiency anemia. There were no cases of protein deficiency, as well as other side metabolic disorders.

Conclusion. LGR is a promising, sufficiently safe and effective operation for obesity, which can be considered both as an independent operation and as the first stage of more complex bariatric surgeries. The maximum average percentage of overweight loss after prostate cancer was 45% at 6-12 months after surgery and depended on the baseline BMI.

After the operation, some patients (68.5%) developed IDA. There were no other long-term metabolic complications of the operation.

Literature

1. Abdullazhanov, B.R., Abdiraimov, B.A., Bozorov, N.E., & Nishanov, M.F. (2011). Primary gastric resection for perforated duodenal ulcers. *Gastroenterology of St. Petersburg*, (2-3), M1-M2.
2. Avoyan, K.M. (2006). Characteristics of persons first recognized as disabled due to gastric ulcer and duodenal ulcer who underwent gastric resection. *Clinical Medicine*, 84 (5), 69-71.
3. Vyalov, S. S. (2016). Efficacy and safety of liposomal iron in the treatment of anemia after gastric or intestinal resection. *Clinical Pharmacology and Therapy*, 25 (4), 42-46.
4. Omarov, T. I. O., & Mailova, A. A. K. (2017). Evaluation of the effectiveness of gastric sleeve in the treatment of obese patients. *Kazan Medical Journal*, 98 (1).
5. Yashkov, Yu.I., Lutsevich, O.E., Bordan, N.S., & Ivleva, O.V. (2016). Longitudinal gastric resection in obesity - the results of 5-year observations. *Clinical and Experimental Surgery*, 4 (1 (11)).